

DMS Interim Workshop, 10/12/2019

Location: Accelerator premises in Leipzig, Germany. Participants were placed in a room where they could work together, distributed in groups of four.

Duration: 2 hours, with a break of 5 minutes.

Equipment: A PowerPoint presentation was used to sequence the different topics of discussion. Sticky notes were used to help participants reflect on their thoughts.

Structure:

The workshop was divided into three blocks, each of them with the same duration (about 30 min.):

- **Startups selection:** A discussion of what approaches to selecting startups the consortium should reproduce for the second iteration of the project, and which approaches should be modified.
- **Acceleration process:** A discussion of what actions were most and least successful in accelerating the participant startups.
- **Services to provide:** A discussion of which type of services should be given emphasis, and which should be reduced.

In order to stimulate a structured discussion, three questions were made in each of the blocks:

1. What went well?
2. What could have gone better?
3. What can we do about it?

Participants would discuss the questions in groups, and then a representative of each group would bring it up to a plenary discussion, recording their answers in short sentences written in sticky notes.

DMS Whitepaper workshop, 12/11/2020

Location: Microsoft Teams. Participants were provided with breakout rooms, in groups of five.

Duration: 2 hours, with a break of 5 minutes.

Equipment: A PowerPoint presentation was used to sequence the different topics of discussion. Google Jamboards were used to help participants reflect on their thoughts.

Structure:

The workshop was divided into three blocks, each of them with the same duration (about 30 min.):

- The most and least successful parts of DMS (15' + 15' report back)
- How to define and assess impact (15'+ 15' report back)
- What would have made DMS more successful? (15' + 15' report back)

Participants would discuss the questions in groups, and then a representative of each group would bring it up to a plenary discussion, recording their answers in short sentences written in sticky notes.